

DESCRIBING MAKSUD SHAIKZODA**Mamurova Feruza Islamovna****Obutjonova Durдона Omonjon kizi**

Tashkent state transport university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10926661>

Annotation: During the 10 years she lived in Tashkent, Shaykhzoda not only mastered the Uzbek language, but also wrote poems and articles in this language, translated Pushkin's works, studied the works of Cholpon, and studied the works of Navoi with love.

Key words: Maqsud Shaikhzada, Tashkent, Oybek, Navoi, articles, scientist, Olim Sharafiddinov, poet, Tesha Salimov.

One of the contemporaries of Maqsud Sheikhzadeh writes: in his memoirs, "The spring of 1938. The rumor that a new, very knowledgeable teacher has arrived at the Department of Literature suddenly spread throughout the institute. Soon after, I had the privilege of meeting the cause of the voice directly at work..." These lines are written by Tesha Salimov, a well-known linguist who has worked at the Tashkent Pedagogical Institute for many years. Although Khotiranavis said that "the new, very knowledgeable teacher arrived at the Pedagogical Institute in 1938, in our opinion, this event happened in the spring of 1939. At that time, the department of Uzbek literature of the institute, along with other creative institutions and higher educational institutions, was hesitant about the 500th anniversary of Navoi. In this regard, an extended meeting of the department was held on the same day, where the head of the department, Scientist Sharafiddinov, gave a lecture on the study of Navoi's literary heritage. The lecture was well received by everyone, including the new teacher. Then there was a discussion on the lecture.

Among those who participated in the discussion, the speech of a young scientist attracted the attention of the audience. According to Tesha Salimov, his impassioned speech was distinguished by its "theoretical foundation, deep scientific interpretation of rich factual materials, ability to clearly and clearly express ideas." This young scholar was Maqsud Shaikhzadeh, a new member of the Department of Uzbek Literature. "Today's meeting," continues Tesha Salimov, "was of particular importance to me." Shaykhzada's thoughts about Navoi, in particular, his wonderful and moving thoughts about the poetics of Navoi's poetry, surprised everyone. But the example of Shaikhzada Navoi's lyrics opened up a whole world of sophistication for me. That's how it happened, I became a loyal fan of Sheikhzadeh. We worked together at the institute for many

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

years. "Sheikhzada became a shining example for me even during the pedagogical work process."

In the early 1950s, when I studied at the Faculty of Philology of the State University of Central Asia (now the National University of Uzbekistan), I listened to the lectures of Docent Tesha Salimov on linguistic issues for some time. The teacher, who knew his field thoroughly, was a very humble, cultured, wonderful person. Such a person admired the knowledge of the "young scientist" about Navoi at that time, so during the 10 years he lived in Tashkent, Sheikhzada not only mastered the Uzbek language, but also wrote poems and articles in this language, translated Pushkin's works, and researched the work of Cholpon. He studied Navoi's work with love. Even when he studied, he was able to debate with Olim Sharafiddinov, the author of the first treatise on the great poet, and was able to charm the members of the Uzbek language and literature department with his knowledge and new views on Navoi.

If we take into account that in those years the study of Navoi's work had just begun, and there were only a few literary experts in this field, such as Olim Sharafiddinov and Oybek, it is known that Shaikhzoda began to discover Navoi almost at the same time as them. So, under the influence of whom or whom, and based on what sources, he began to study Navoi's life and work? We know very well that Shaykhzoda met Oybek and Gafur Ghulam during his service in "Sharq Haqiqat" newspaper and learned the Uzbek language with their help. We are aware that Shaykhzoda studied at the Institute of Language and Literature of the Science Committee, and during his short term at this institute, he had close relations with Fitrat, Otajon Hashim and Oybek.

It is known that since 1928, Oybek was interested in the personality of Navoi and began to study reliable sources about him. It can be assumed that Oibek shared the new and strange information he received from these sources during his conversations with Sheikhzadeh, and gave him the impetus to ignite his feelings of love for the great Uzbek poet. Moreover, in 1924, Cholpon, who began to study his work in Sheikhzadeh, and was in frequent communication with him, announced that the 500th anniversary of Navoi's birth was approaching and put the issue of serious study of the great poet's work on the agenda. Perhaps Cholpon also contributed a lot to the "pollination" of Shaikhzada with Navoi's work. In any case, when he came to work at the pedagogical institute, he was recognized as one of the connoisseurs of Navoi's work. When talking about Sheikhzada's rich knowledge of Navoi and the reasons for this knowledge, it is permissible to refer to Tesha Salimov again. "The secret

of Sheikhzada's knowledge," he wrote, "was the excellence, breadth and depth of his reading." The main of these three factors, which is the secret of Sheikhzadeh's knowledge, is the "excellence of reading". Sheikhzadeh, like all scholars of the past, gained knowledge through reading. He also studied Navoi's life and work through private reading.

In 1938, Sheikhzade published the articles "The great figure of our classical literature" in the "Teachers' newspaper" and "The problem of love in Khamsa" in the "Yosh Leninchi" newspaper, which revealed that he had already entered the world of Navoi in those years.

In 1938-1941, William Shakespeare, Nizami Ganjavi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Muhammad Aminkhoja Muqimi, A.N. Radishchev, M.Yu. Lermontov, N.G. Chernyshevsky, A.P. Chekhov, A.M. Gorky, V. Writers such as V. Mayakovsky, M. F. Okhundov, Henri Barbus wrote dozens of articles about writers and did not forget the great Uzbek poet. On the contrary, Navoi Sheikhzada was at the center of his literary criticism. In addition to the two articles mentioned above, he wrote "The image of a woman in Navoi" (1939), "Navoi is the most cultured person of his time", "Navoi is a patriot", "Navoi's work and socialist culture", "The passionate singer of science and enlightenment", "Navoi and Babur" (1940), "Navoi and Youth", "Great Educator", "The Matter of Honesty in Navoi", "Folklore Motifs in Navoi's Work", "Great Poet" and the brochure "Genial Poet"

Shaykhzada, with his literary and critical articles and a scientific treatise, made an important contribution to the science of Navoi studies, which began to be born in this period, and it would be no mistake to say that he was one of the founders of this science.

References:

1. Mamurova, F. I. (2021, May). ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 176-178).
2. Mamurova, F. I., & ugli Abdubahabov, A. A. (2023). TWO FOLK POETS. "TRENDS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND PRACTICE", 1(3), 23-30.
3. Islomovna, M. F., & Abduvoxob o'g'li, A. A. (2023, January). Maqsud Shayxzodaning Hayoti Va Ijodi. In Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences (USA) (pp. 19-20).
4. Mamurova, F. I. (2021, May). ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 176-178).
5. Islamovna, Mamurova Feruza. "MAQSUD SHAYKHZADEH-TWO FOLK DILBANDI." INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGY AND LINGUISTICS. Vol. 1. No. 1. 2024.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

6. Islamovna, M. F. (2024, January). MAQSUD SHAYKHZADEH-TWO FOLK DILBANDI. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGY AND LINGUISTICS (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 189-192).
7. Islomovna, M. F. (2024). O 'ZBEK ADABIYOTINING ATOQLI NAMOYANDALARIDAN BIRI MAQSUD SHAYXZODNING "JALOLIDDIN MANGUBERDI" ASARI. Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(1), 89-92.
8. Islamovna, M. F. (2024). THE CREATION OF MAQSUD SHAYKHZODA-AS A GOLDEN LEGACY. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(1), 90-93.
9. Islamovna, Mamurova Feruza. "MAQSUD SHAYKHZADEH-TWO FOLK DILBANDI." INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGY AND LINGUISTICS. Vol. 1. No. 1. 2024.

